

LOCK-IN THERMOGRAPHY FOR INSPECTION OF A HOLE DEFECT IN DENTAL COMPOSITE RESTORATION

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1 Introduction

Composite resins in combination with the acid-etch technique and adhesive systems have been used for the restoration of tooth caries and cervical lesions because of their superior mechanical and physical properties, and excellent esthetics. Newly formulated bonding systems and advanced etching techniques (total-etching, self-etching) may provide a better adhesion of the composite resin to dentin from chemical and physical viewpoints. The formation of resin tags into open dentinal tubules and the hybridization of the exposed collagenous network of the intertubular dentin establish the adhesive micromechanical retention of the restoration in dentin [1, 2].

Evaluation of marginal integrity at the composite resin-tooth interface is required for clinically successful restorations. Polymerization contraction of the composite resin filled in the cavity arises during light curing. This contraction competes with the bond strength and may cause marginal disintegration and insufficient sealing of open dentinal tubules, especially in the dentin segments. Sealing ability and bond strength of adhesive systems to dentin are still lower than those to enamel segments [3]. Marginal gap formation leads to leakage, which may bring about marginal discoloration, secondary caries or partial loss of the restoration [4, 5]. Therefore, achieving complete adhesion and evaluating the adherend are important. Marginal disintegration of adhesively placed fillings has been analyzed by scanning electron microscopy and by microleakage determination using dye penetration [6, 7]. In the case of SEM analysis, only defects that appeared on the surface can be observed and the examination of the margin is subjective and labor intensive. Through these studies, restored tooth

specimens have to be sectioned vertically to observe the internal debonding.

Lock-in thermography utilizes an infrared camera to detect the surface temperature of a thermal wave propagating into the material and then produces phase or amplitude images[8,9]. Lock-in thermography can be used to detect subsurface defects through the differences in phase or amplitude. Lock-in thermography has two main advantages in comparison to steady-state thermography: an improved signal-to-noise ratio and a better spatial resolution. In the low sampling, because this method can sense the minute change of the surface, defect and failure detection are possible in the small phase change. The phase change image has the advantage that the error by the non-uniformity of the object surface emissivity is small.

In this study, digital lock-in correlation method was exploited to calculate amplitude and phase images about subsurface defects. The composite restoration specimen with flat bottomed hole defects of various depths and diameters was made. The purpose of this study is to investigate the feasibility on detection of a hole defect in dental composite restoration using the lock-in infrared thermography.

2 Digital Lock-in Correlation Method

Fig. 1(a) shows the principle of the digital lock-in correlation procedure. Lock-in thermography makes use of periodic optical stimulation to heat the sample, using sinusoidally modulated halogen lamps [10, 11]. The term lock-in refers to the monitoring of the exact time difference between the output signal and the reference input signal. Hence, amplitude and phase images of the reconstructed thermal wave can be computed for each heat-generating frequency by

post-processing the recorded image data using the Fourier transform algorithm.

The signal detected from the basis function can be shown as follows:

$$S = \frac{1}{nN} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^n K_j F_{i,j} \quad (1)$$

where $F_{i,j}$ denotes the temperature measurement at the time of the j -th frame in the i -th lock-in period. The weighting factors K_j are given by

$$K_j^{0^\circ} = 2\sin\left(\frac{2\pi(j-1)}{n}\right) \quad (2)$$

$$K_j^{90^\circ} = 2\cos\left(\frac{2\pi(j-1)}{n}\right) \quad (3)$$

The amplitude A and the signal phase Φ can easily be retrieved from the two results S^{0° and S^{90° . Then, the amplitude (A) and the phase (Φ) are:

$$A = \sqrt{(S^{0^\circ})^2 + (S^{90^\circ})^2} \quad (4)$$

$$\Phi = \arctan\left(\frac{S^{90^\circ}}{S^{0^\circ}}\right) \quad (5)$$

3 Experimental

3.1 Specimen preparation

Specimens were prepared as shown in Fig. 2. Penetration ring type acryl substrate (inner diameter 10 mm, outer diameter 12 mm, height 3 mm) was prepared. A dentin adhesive (Clearfil S3, Kuraray, Japan) was applied onto the inner surface of the ring substrate following the manufacturer's instruction. After gently air-blowing the coated adhesive layer, it was photocured for 10 sec with a light-emitting diode (LED) light source with wave lengths of 420-480 nm and a power density of 1000mW/cm² (Pencure, Morita, Japan). This was done to stabilize the states of self-etching, uniform wetting and cross linking of the bonding agents. Then a composite resin (Clearfil AP-X, Kuraray, Japan) was tightly packed inside the ring. The resin that was placed as one bulk light-cured (LED, Pencure, Morita, Japan) from the upper surface for 20s. A tungsten carbide end-mill tool of 5 mm in diameter (YG, 3S MILLS,

Fig. 1 Principle of the digital Lock-in thermography correlation procedure(a) and complex vector representation of the amplitude and phase relations in the two channel lock-in process (b) [12]

Korea) driven at a high rotation speed and a very low feeding speed, under a water spray, was used to make the tooth cavity. Fig. 3 shows a schematic of the restoration specimens containing hole defects with various sizes. As shown in Fig. 3(a), various hole diameters were prepared with the same composite thickness of 0.5 mm. Various hole depths were also made with the same diameter of 5 mm(Fig. 3(b)).

The surface of all the specimens was painted with a block flat sprayer(1249 flat black, TESTORS, USA) and maintained a high emissivity of 0.95 that is close to the black body. Applying the uniform black paint of a high emissivity may increase the surface emissivity, reduce the secondary reflections and provide a uniformly emissive surface.

Fig. 2 Schematic of restoration specimens containing various holes

Fig. 3 Schematic of experimental set-up for lock-in thermography

3.2 Set-up for lock-in infrared thermography

Fig. 3 shows a schematic of experimental set-up for lock-in infrared thermography used in this study. For generation of sine waves of a single frequency, a programmable software (IRBIS 3 plus system) and a controller were used. The entire upper surface of the specimens was heated with a modulated heat wave from the 500 W halogen lamp kept approximately 50 cm away from the specimen. The heat source was driven by the lock-in module which was controlled by the IRBIS 3 plus system software. The heat

source and the infrared camera signals were synchronized. The surface temperature field was measured with a radiometric infrared camera (Vario cam, JENOPTIK, Germany) equipped with a 640×480 pixels detector. The spectral range of the camera was 7.5–14 μm and a thermal sensitivity was 0.05K. Experimental conditions were a halogen lamp pulse-duty factor of 50 %, a lock-in period of 5 times and a camera frame rate of 12 Hz. Lock-in frequency range was 0.006-2 Hz.

4 Results and discussion

4.1 Effects of the hole diameter

Fig. 4 shows the surface temperature evolution. Since the lock-in thermography uses the same heat source of the halogen lamp, the surface temperature of the holed region in accordance with the lessened composite thickness is to be higher than the sound area. The amplitude contrast in the thermal images is generated by this surface temperature difference. As shown in Fig. 5, amplitude image showed some differences in detection images according to the frequency and hole size. At a frequency of 0.05 Hz, a clear contrast of the hole image was shown. The contrast difference between the sound and the holed regions can be given by the equation,

$$C = \frac{A_h - A_s}{A_s} \quad (6)$$

Here, A_h is calculated with the average amplitude of the hole image pixels including boundary data. A_s is the average of pixel data for the sound part.

Fig. 6 shows the amplitude contrast difference as a function of the lock-in frequency. The frequency range in which the hole image was distinctive similar to the visual image was 0.01-0.3 Hz. The highest contrast was shown up at 0.05 Hz. The hole diameters of 2 mm and 3 mm showed the contrast difference which was large around 0.05 Hz in which their values were smaller than that of 5 mm diameter case. At a lock-in frequency of 0.006 Hz, the halogen lamp has long light-on duration at the same pulse-duty (50%). Thus it irradiated a large heat quantity in the specimen where the specimen surface

heat was saturated to lessen the contrast difference of the amplitude. On the contrary at 0.3 Hz and

Fig. 4 Surface temperature variation of a test sample (diameter: 5 mm, $f_{lock-in}$: 0.01 Hz)

Fig. 5 Optical photo and amplitude images of holed specimens at various frequencies and hole diameters

higher frequencies, the heat was insufficiently supplied in the specimen so that the temperature differential at the hole and sound region influenced by the heat conduction was small. It is because good heat-conduction in the soundness part

Fig. 6 Amplitude contrast ratio as a function of lock-in frequency according to hole diameters

Fig. 7 SNR of amplitudes as a function of lock-in frequency according to hole diameters

Fig. 8 Contrast ratio and SNR in amplitude analysis as a function of the hole diameter

led to a decrease in the contrast as compared with that of the holed region. As to the hole diameter of 1 mm, detection was impossible at the present lock-in frequencies.

Signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) was calculated by the absolute value of the difference between the amplitude averages in the holed and the sound region, divided by the standard deviation (σ_s) of the sound region data

$$SNR = \frac{|A_h - A_s|}{\sigma_s} \quad (7)$$

The SNR may offer a quantified detectable thermal image. SNR results as a function of lock-in frequency were plotted in Fig. 7. The SNR value was relatively high at 0.05 Hz, which was similarly observed in the contrast ratio result. In the amplitude

Fig. 9 Phase images of a specimen according to various frequency conditions and defect diameters

image, the contrast ratio and SNR begin to appear at 0.01 Hz. The boundary portion was observable at 0.05 Hz with the hole diameter of 5 mm. The contrast ratio showed a drastic increase more than SNR. The relative difference was quite different according to lock-in frequency and hole diameter(Fig. 8).

Fig 9 shows phase (Φ) images. At 0.01 and 0.5 Hz, contrast of the sound region was rather clear but the boundary was ambiguous under the noise which was serious at frequencies beyond 1 Hz. Through the phase image, the big hole diameter of 5 mm caused large contrast ratios at 0.006 Hz and 0.5 Hz. Hole diameters of 2 mm and 3 mm gave quite large contrasts at 0.3 Hz(Fig. 10). With decreasing the frequency below the critical value, the phase difference was enlarged in the negative due to the heat saturation of the specimen surface.

On the other hand, the detection of the hole was possible in the phase test in the range 0.006 Hz to 0.8Hz. At 0.006Hz, SNR result for 5 mm hole diameter had large values, which indicates a clear thermal image of the hole.

Fig. 10 Phase contrast ratio as a function of lock-in frequency according to hole diameters

Fig. 11 SNR of phase as a function of lock-in frequency according to hole diameters

Fig. 12 Contrast ratio and SNR in phase analysis as a function of hole diameter

SNR in the phase was high in the present frequencies except 0.05 Hz. For the hole diameters 2 mm and 3 mm, SNR value was high at 0.3 Hz, where contrast ratio was also high (Fig. 11). At 0.01 Hz and 0.5 Hz, the contrast ratio and SNR increased as the hole diameter increased. The contrast ratio increased more drastic than SNR, and offered the most clear image of the phase at the hole diameter of 5 mm (Fig. 12).

4.2 Effects of the composite resin thickness

Fig. 13 shows amplitude images of the 0.5 mm composite thickness (t_d) specimen. At a lock-in frequency of 0.05 Hz, composite thickness of 0.5 mm provided a clear and good quality image. Fig 14 shows the amplitude contrast difference as a function of the lock-in frequency according to the composite thicknesses. The frequency range in which the hole defect image was distinctive and similar to in the visual image was 0.01-0.1 Hz. The amplitude difference showed the tendency to decrease due to the heat quantity of the specimen surface at the very low lock-in frequency below 0.01 Hz. The highest contrast was shown up at 0.05 Hz for the composite thickness of 0.5 mm. The composite thicknesses of 1 mm and 1.5 mm showed the contrast difference which was large around 0.025 Hz. However, for the composite thickness of 2 mm, detection was impossible under the frequency conditions given in this study. SNR results as a function of lock-in frequency were plotted in Fig 15. At 0.01 Hz, the SNR was high for the three composite thicknesses. For composite thickness of 0.5 mm, SNR maintained still high at 0.05 Hz.

Fig. 13 Optical photo and the corresponding amplitude images of a specimen according to frequency conditions (t_d : 0.5 mm).

Fig. 14 Amplitude contrast ratio as a function of lock-in frequency according to composite thicknesses

Fig. 15 SNR of amplitude results as a function of lock-in frequency according to composite thicknesses

Fig 16 shows the phase images for the composite thickness of 0.5 mm. Contrary to the above amplitude images, contrast between the sound and hole region was clear at 0.01 and 0.5 Hz. As calculated by equation (6), the contrast ratio of the 0.5 mm composite thickness was high at 0.006 and

Fig. 16 Phase images of a specimen according to frequency conditions (t_d : 0.5 mm)

Fig. 17 Phase contrast ratio as a function of lock-in frequency according to composite thickness

Fig. 18 SNR of phase results as a function of lock-in frequency according to composite thickness

0.5 Hz (Fig. 17). At this condition, the absolute SNR was high (Fig. 18). For the composite thickness of 1 mm, phase contrast was the highest at 0.1 Hz. But the phase difference was quite enlarged in the range less than the frequency at the minimized SNR.

4 Conclusions

Artificial hole defects in dental composite restoration are detected using a lock-in

thermography method. Amplitude and phase images of the specimens were analyzed according to the lock-in frequency and the thickness of holes. The infrared lock-in thermography method showed the effective optimum condition for detecting the hole in dental composite restoration.

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